

interaction OfferRankingSequence

r2rTC: Shopping
Orchestratorrank:
OfferEnricherAndRankerofferC:
OfferCategorizerincp:
IncentiveProvidersynch:
DriverPassengerSynchronizerprefManager:
Preference Manager

R2RModel::R2R_DetailedClasses

Also operations for deleting and modifying a ride

Requirement Req3 allows Passenger to enable/disable incentives

Requirement Req10 mandates an optional preference during a mobility request

Requirement Req12 a Passenger profile can include optional personal information such as job, salary etc. The ProfileUpdate functionality allows such changes

InProfile if True, it means that the Traveller has specified that preference in the profile, if False, it means that they specified during the mobility request, the previously specified preference might not be valid anymore.

TravellerPreference Class refers to the preferences that either Driver or Passenger can have them

In the UI we might want to allocate predefined categorical sizes

"similarity": Shows the degree of belonging to the cluster

«enumeration» PreferenceImportanceValue
0
0.5
1
1.5
2
2.5
3
3.5
4
4.5
5

«enumeration» Language
Dutch
English
Finnish
French
German
Greek
Italian
Swedish

«enumeration» SeatType
Baby
Front
Back
Aisle
Window

«enumeration» DriverPreferenceType
Chattiness
CulturalInterest
RadioAllowed

«enumeration» ItineraryCategoryType
Fast
EcoFriendly
Economic

«enumeration» PassengerPreferenceType
VehicleCondition
TransportationMode
RadioControl
Safety

«enumeration» HealthIssueType
Deafness
Pregnant
Visual
Walking

«enumeration» AidToolType
Crutches
ManualWheelChair
MotoredWheelChair
Walker

«enumeration» ComfortClass
First
Business
Smart
Economy

«enumeration» PassengerClusterType
CommuterPassenger
EnvironmentallyFriendlyPerson

«enumeration» Gender
Female
Male
Other

«enumeration» PetType
Bird
Cat
Dog

«enumeration» PetSize
Small
Medium
Large

«enumeration» ItemSpecialCare
Fragile
CabinOnly
Positioning
FridgeDependent

«enumeration» IndividualTransportType
Van
MotorCycle
SUV

«enumeration» DriverClusterType
CommuterDriver

